

Anthropologie

Zeitschrift für Medizinethnologie • Journal of Medical Anthropology

hrsg. von/edited by: Arbeitsgemeinschaft Ethnomedizin e.V. – AGEM

Zum Titelbild/Front picture *Curare* 36(2013)3:

The photo shows the setting of an interview between Prof. William Sax, South Asia Institute, University of Heidelberg, and Walid Darwish Zamzam, who practices Islamic healing in UK. Mr. Zamzam gave a lecture on „Islamic Healing: a practitioner’s point of view“ at Heidelberg on 02 July, 2013. The interview can be found on pages 168–171 of this issue.

Die letzten Hefte:

Curare 35(2012)4: Objekte sammeln, sehen und deuten. Die Sprache der Objekte

Curare 36(2013)1+2: Medizinethnologische Diskurse um Körpermodifikationen im interkulturellen Arbeitsfeld Ethnologie und Medizin

Die nächsten Hefte:

Curare 36(2013)4 zu Themen aus der Transkulturellen Psychologie

Curare 36(2014) zur Ethnobotanik und Ethnopharmakologie

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**Zeitschrift für Medizinethnologie
Journal of Medical Anthropology**
Herausgeber im Auftrag der / Editor-in-chief on behalf of:

Arbeitsgemeinschaft Ethnomedizin e.V. – AGEM

Ekkehard Schröder (auch V.i.S.d.P.) mit

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IMPRESSUM *Curare* 36(2013)3**Verlag und Vertrieb / Publishing House:**

VWB – Verlag für Wissenschaft und Bildung, Amand Aglaster
Postfach 11 03 68 • 10833 Berlin, Germany
Tel. +49-[0]30-251 04 15 • Fax: +49-[0]30-251 11 36
e-mail: info@vwb-verlag.com
<http://www.vwb-verlag.com>

Bezug / Supply:

Der Bezug der *Curare* ist im Mitgliedsbeitrag der Arbeitsgemeinschaft Ethnomedizin (AGEM) enthalten. Einzelne Hefte können beim VWB-Verlag bezogen werden // *Curare* is included in a regular membership of AGEM. Single copies can be ordered at VWB-Verlag.

Abonnementspreis / Subscription Rate:

Die jeweils gültigen Abonnementspreise finden Sie im Internet unter // Valid subscription rates you can find at the internet under: www.vwb-verlag.com/reihen/Periodika/curare.html

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ISSN 0344-8622

ISBN 978-3-86135-774-2

Die Artikel dieser Zeitschrift wurden einem Gutachterverfahren unterzogen // This journal is peer reviewed.

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Redaktionsschluss: 15.07.2013

Lektorat und Endredaktion: EKKEHARD SCHRÖDER

Die Artikel der *Curare* werden einem Reviewprozess unterzogen / The journal *Curare* is a peer-reviewed journal**Addenda und Errata zu Curare 36(2013)1+2:**• *Addendum: BMI vom Schreibtisch:*

In *Curare* 36(2013)1+2 auf S. 12 und in der Anmerkung 23 zitiert die Autorin DEBORA FROMMELD in ihrem Beitrag „Fit statt fett“: *Der Body-Mass-Index als biopolitisches Instrument* Zeitungsberichte über Verbeamtungswünsche, die wegen eines abweichenden BMIs abgelehnt werden. Im geschilderten Falle handelte es sich um einen Polizeianwärter mit einem ausgeprägt trainierten muskulösen Körper. Wie zu erfahren ist, gelang es dem Bewerber, nach einem Gerichtsverfahren doch noch eingestellt zu werden. Hier die beiden Quellen: <http://www.derwesten.de/wr/wr-info/zu-muskuloes-fuer-den-polizeidienst-id76939.html> • <http://www.derwesten.de/wr/staedte/schwelm/muskelspiel-vor-gericht-gewonnen-id348813.html>

• *Addendum und Erratum zu Autor Valšík:*

Der Erstautor des Artikels “Popular Medicine and Traditional Mutilations in Egyptian Nubia” von VALŠÍK J.A. & HUSSIEEN F.H. in *Curare* 36(2013)1+2: 86–92 heißt nicht Jan A. Valšík, sondern JINDŘICH A. VALŠÍK (s. S. 89). Eine neuere Diplomarbeit ist seinem Leben und Werk gewidmet (Diplomovka-Vymazalová-Valšík), Brno (Brünn) [<http://www.uschovna.cz/en/package/P8X3L3SBFK7ELFBL-MAT>]. Information von Assoc. Prof. Rado Beňuš, Bratislava, Head of the Department of Anthropology of the Faculty of Natural Sciences of CU, where Prof. Valšík used to work. (benus@nic.fns.uniba.sk).

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Is it Wise to Use “Culture” as Category in the Sector of Health-Care?

YVONNE SCHAFFLER

Abstract Health care workers often stress that migrants are a disturbing factor in clinical routine work. Due to their “cultural otherness” migrants are said to be in need of special attention, their lack of language skills, in particular, is a source of problems. Scientists, NGO’s and the media have realized this and have thought about it. I do not intend to discuss the variety of concepts of culture as they are discussed in anthropology, cultural studies, philosophy, or sociology. I rather criticise the tendency in medicine to attribute “cultural problems” to foreign patients, who therefore require a certain “cultural competence” on behalf of the health care workers. My argument is that the use of “culture” as a category outside the humane discipline bears the risk of its reification. This is noticeable when people think of “culture” in relationship to national boundaries or religious membership. I thus want to encourage a more accurate communication, especially when we are directing our concern towards the public. My appeal applies in particular to the situations, where extreme right wing Austrian politicians like Jörg Haider or Heinz Christian Strache and authors like the German social-democrat Thilo Sarrazin have agitated the political situation to the general disadvantage of immigrants.

Keywords Migrants and healthcare – culturalization – racism – social milieus

Ist „Kultur“ eine valide Kategorie im Gesundheitsbereich?

Zusammenfassung MigrantInnen gelten als „Sand im Getriebe“ des klinischen Alltags – zumindest wird dies von Seiten des Gesundheitspersonals oft so dargestellt und von WissenschaftlerInnen, NGOs sowie den Medien erforscht bzw. aufgegriffen. Die Hauptargumente, die besondere Aufmerksamkeit auf gerade jene Gruppe rechtfertigen sollen, sind fehlende Sprachkenntnisse und die Zugehörigkeit zu einer „anderen“ Kultur. Dabei ist fraglich, ob „Kultur“ tatsächlich als valide Kategorie gelten kann, wenn es darum geht, wem innerhalb des Gesundheitssystems wie viel Aufmerksamkeit zu Teil wird. Problematisch ist, dass der Kulturbegriff meist in Übereinstimmung mit Staatsgrenzen oder religiöser Zugehörigkeit angewandt wird, obwohl sich auch in Österreich und Deutschland zahlreiche „Kulturen“ im Sinn von sozialen Milieus finden, deren Ausdruck dem behandelnden Gesundheitspersonal mindestens ebenso fremd ist wie jener von „MigrantInnen“. Ich möchte daher zu einer präziseren Kommunikation anregen, wenn wir uns als WissenschaftlerInnen an die Öffentlichkeit wenden. Dies gilt im Speziellen, wenn es um Länder geht, wo rechts außen stehende PolitikerInnen wie Jörg Haider oder Heinz Christian Strache in Österreich oder auch Autoren wie der deutsche Sozialdemokrat Thilo Sarrazin ein politisches Klima geschaffen haben, das zu Lasten von MigrantInnen geht.

Keywords Immigration und Gesundheit – Kulturalisierung – Rassismus – Soziale Milieus

Introduction

This essay is based on some critical reflections on the use of categories such as “culture” and “migrants” in the sector of health-care. The underlying ideas were presented at Workshop 37 of the German Anthropological Association conference in Vienna

from September 14th to 17th 2011. The reactions to my lecture were mixed. Some people felt that I was generally discarding culture as a concept to think and make sense with, when it comes to healthcare. This is not the case. My concern is rather to encourage specifying what and whom we mean when writing about culture or migrants. In some cases it

* A preliminary version of this paper was presented at the Workshop 37 of the biannual conference of the German Anthropological Association (Deutsche Gesellschaft für Völkerkunde) in Vienna, September 14–17, 2011. The Conference was titled “Ist ‘Kultur’ eine valide Kategorie im Gesundheitsbereich?” (“Is ‘Culture’ a Valid Category in Healthcare?”) The workshop was chaired by Ruth Kutalek and Ekkehard Schröder and titled “Wie die Medizin auf die ‘Kultur’ kam. Oder: was hat Kultur mit Struktur zu tun? Medizinanthropologische Ansätze zur interkulturellen Forschung in der Medizin.” (“How ‘culture’ came into medicine. Or: What has culture to do with structure? Medical Anthropological approaches for an intercultural research in biomedicine”).

may be better to split “culture” into its qualities like language, tradition, values or orientations¹, or to replace it with a more accurate concept, for example “social milieu”.

Becoming aware of a violent discourse in the online media

I began to question the meaningfulness of “culture” as category after I had been interviewed together with Ekkehard Schröder for an article for a rather liberal Austrian daily newspaper. I was asked about possible problems that migrants and health care workers face when encountering each other in a clinical setting². I liked the resulting article, because it reflected my answers in a proper way, but felt alarmed when I checked the 17 reader comments underneath the online version. Though I’m aware of the fact that the opinions expressed in online media do not necessarily represent the public opinion I found the negativity expressed in the postings remarkable. Someone stated that alcohol in medication being a problem for Muslim patients is “ridiculous”. Or Muslims who hold on to their traditional beliefs so strongly should not be treated by our modern physicians, but rather by Allah. Another person felt that migrants who disturb other patients by welcoming their large families to their sick bed should better leave the country and follow their customs elsewhere. I switched to a similar article on “cultural differences in pain perception”³ and came across an even fiercer debate encompassing altogether 134 postings, most of them composed in a language of hatred. One poster even suggested that we should “teach” immigrants our “culture of suffering” by administering them Truxal^{®4} and confining them to latticed bedsteads and the wearing of strait jackets. Unfortunately, more “adequate” measures, such as electroshocking, waterbeds or lobotomy is forbidden in Austria (which by the way is not fully true, but this is not the point). Another news article I checked related to the fact that immigrants make less use of preventive health measures than Austrians.⁵ The reasons therefore are said to lie in a lack of knowledge and religious barriers. The article was inspired by a manual published by the Austrian Medical Chamber (Ärztchamber) on how doctors should deal with migrants (PEINTINGER 2011) and by a survey edited by the Austrian Fund for Integration

(MAYER 2011), which I intend to discuss in detail later. The publishing medium was a rather conservative Austrian daily newspaper. The arguments of the exclusively negative reactions are as follows:

- People migrate to our country in order to abuse our health system
- People who suffer from a disease should generally be refused immigration in order to delimit its abuse
- Immigrants are to blame themselves if they are in bad health because they only eat unhealthy food
- Immigrants who refuse to learn German should not be supported during clinical encounters because otherwise they will never learn our language.

As I went through further contributions on similar topics I faced the same predominance of hateful statements. The style of their drafting, of course, depended on the medium.

The political co-option of the term “culture”

I think that we owe those negative reactions partly to the fact that almost everyone fears (or de facto feels) that they will not be treated adequately when in need of medical attendance, especially when considering the public funds that finance our health system are becoming increasingly scarce. I realized this after I started paying attention to complaints regarding health care by my friends and family. Their general practitioner would not to listen to their chest or measure their fever anymore, they said. Or the orthopaedist did not even touch their hurting bones. They were sent home with a broken leg without having been given a proper plaster cast. Being sick puts people in a vulnerable position and not been properly cared for is a horrible thought. The idea that despite scarce funds in public health financing we not only afford to help migrants with their health problems but we even pay special attention to needs arising from so called “cultural factors”, seems to many people to be beyond the bearable. But even if my speculation is right that Austrians are afraid of not receiving sufficient medical attention, if we are too generous with our resources, it still remains open what inspires this kind of fear. For a deeper explanation we need to reflect on our political climate and how the term “culture” is used in everyday

language. According to APPADURAI (1996:12ff) and BASU (2011) “culture” is often confused nowadays, or interchangeably used with concepts of “ethnicity”, “nation”, “language” or “religion”. For this very reason BRABEC DE MORI (2011:15f) decided to use it only when talking about creative productions, such as cultural events. He explains his decision with the multi-layeredness of the term and the general tendency to confuse its meanings, rendering that “culture” in its oldest meaning as “cultivation” which connotes a process of cultivation or improvement, as in agriculture or horticulture. Another level of meaning would describe culture as something that one either possesses or not; as something that is useful to isolate one group from another, e.g. by distinguishing the “cultivated” Romans from the “barbaric” tribes that surrounded them. He points out that using culture in this normative sense was scientifically correct at least until the early 20th century, as we know from the ethnological works of Gunter Tessmann, who distinguished “primitive” from “civilized peoples”. Then a new level of meaning developed historically from the former. It emerged in the 20th century when “culture” became a concept central to anthropology, encompassing all human phenomena that are not purely results of human genetics (compare also KNIPPER & BILGIN 2009:21f). We consequently learned that all peoples possess culture; not only some that show specific characteristics. But even this now “positive” use implicates problems: The discovery that all peoples “possess culture” led to the popular conclusion that these peoples “are” cultures. “Culture” since there serves to demarcate a drawing line between the different cultures.

Especially right-wing populists have made use of the term, arguing that people from “other cultures” can hardly integrate themselves into ours due to too much “cultural difference”. It seems that “culture,” by turning it into a nation-like and thus rigid category, nowadays applies just as “race” in earlier times (FREDERICSON 2004: Introduction). Words like “migration”, “multicultural,” or “Muslim” have thus developed into stimulus words that evoke negative associations. The fact that Islamic religion is not part of the “native Austrian culture” has inspired the content of an election slogan (“Daham statt Islam,” meaning “at Home is better than Islam”) for the general election in Austria in 2006. In the same campaign Austrian culture was aligned

with blood and soil, proposing “more courage for our Viennese blood,” referring to the Viennese operetta culture⁶. In Germany the term “culture” has been politically co-opted even more openly in the context of the debate around a supposed German “leading culture” (“Leitkultur”), which should be respected by immigrants in that they orient themselves towards German “cultural principles.” The conservative party of Bavaria (CSU=Christian-Social Union) defines those as composed of language, history, tradition and “Christian-occidental” values. On a European level, conservatives like David Cameron, Angela Merkel or Nicolas Sarkozy posed the concept of “Multikulti”⁷ as a threat because it would impede the integration of immigrants into the culture of their host nation. The situation in Austria is aggravated by the fact that newspapers cite immigrants almost exclusively in the context of problems or conflicts, especially when it comes to tabloid newspaper (ZAUENER 2012). In an atmosphere like this it has become very difficult to write about migration and health without doing harm to those we actually want to support. Even though we are quick to warn against a “culturalization” (SCHRÖDER *et al.* 2006) of symptoms or against considering only the geographical origin instead of the individual, the reader grasps the message that immigrants take away valuable resources excessively from our fragile health care system. Provocative media headlines that frame our interviews such as “cries of pain and the forbidden pork”⁸ only help to convey negative emotions, especially since the eating of pork has become a symbol of “our occidental lifestyle.” Even though studies suggest that migrants are more often affected by somatoform pain disorders such as chronic pelvic pain (ALTUNBAY BASIBÜYÜK 2011), depression, dissociative disorders and psychosis (MACHLEIDT 2007a, 2007b) it is a harmful exaggeration to classify them as “sick migrants.”⁹

From “cultural” to “milieu-specific” problems

Even though we have little influence on the wording of media articles I consider it important to avoid any kind of generalization, both in publishing and when being interviewed. I am aware of the fact that the de facto existing problems revealed in studies about migration and health won’t cease to exist only because we change our conceptualization. But we

Fig. 1: Sinus milieus in Austria.

The y-axis shows the social condition according to social position (1 = Upper class/upper middle class, 2 = Middle class, 3 = Lower middleclass/lower class). The x-axis displays three sets of basic orientations from tradition to new orientation (A = Tradition: Performance of duty, order. B = Modernisation: Individualisation, personal fulfilment, pleasure. C = New Orientation: Multi-optionality, pragmatism/refocusing, new syntheses. Milieus: Traditionalists, conservatives, established, adaptive bourgeois, consume oriented basis, performers, adaptive pragmatics, hedonists and digital individualists. (Source: Integral Markt- und Meinungsforschungsges. m. b. H. 2011 by the courtesy of Sinus/Heidelberg and Integral/Wien)

should not contribute to the negative image the general population has about migrants. To begin with I suggest pointing out more vigorously that neither all types of migrants require especial attention in medical care, nor that the problems between migrants and health care workers are caused primarily by “cultural difference.” For a better differentiation between the different types of migrants I propose an alternative to “culture” that allows for a more finely tuned distinction.

Based on ethnographic investigations in the Greater Boston area, DELVECCHIO GOOD and colleagues published an anthology with the somewhat provocative title “shattering culture”. They point out that the new immigration during the last decades led to a cultural environment of hyperdiversity “in which broad identity-based indicators of cultural difference are often too blunt to capture current so-

cial and individual identities” (DELVECCHIO GOOD *et al.* 2011: 3). The French sociologist Bourdieu reacted decades ago to the societal fragmentation we face especially in urban areas. He developed a concept built on two dimensions: A vertical (social class) and a horizontal (culture), adding the horizontal dimension after he had recognized that social reality could not be explained only by economical inequalities. Both dimensions influence the life of an individual and work according to different principles (THIEME 2008). BECK (1986) pointed out for the German speaking area that human behaviour has become increasingly flexible due to higher incomes, longer spans of leisure time, a higher degree of education and more social security. HRADIL (2001) subsequently developed the concept of “social milieus.” Milieus are groups of people that live under certain environmental conditions and/or share cer-

Fig. 2: Life-milieus of migrants in Germany 2008.

Sinus milieu in Austria The y-axis shows the social condition according to social position (1 = Upper class/upper middle class, 2 = Middle class, 3 = Lower middleclass/lower class). The x-axis displays three sets of basic orientations from tradition to new orientation (A = Tradition: Performance of duty, order. B = Modernisation: Individualisation, personal fulfilment, pleasure. C = New Orientation: Multi-optionality, pragmatism/refocusing, new syntheseses. Milieus: Traditionalists, conservatives, established, adaptive bourgeois, consume oriented basis, performers, adaptive pragmatics, hedonists and digital individualists. (Source: Integral Markt- und Meinungsforschungsges. m. b. H. 2011 by the courtesy of Sinus/Heidelberg and Integral/Wien)

tain values. Those who belong to the same social milieu interpret and shape their environment in a similar way. Each milieu can thus be distinguished from others. The market research institution ‘Sinus Sociovision Institut’ at Heidelberg developed the so-called sinus-methodology for research on social milieus. Basically, they see people as tending towards three sets of values in corresponding milieus: 1. “tradition”; 2. “modernism”; 3. “new identities (loss of cultural identity and belonging to a specific group)”. For the general population of Austria the following milieus have been established: Traditionalists (15%), conservatives (6%), established (9%), adaptive bourgeois (15%), consume oriented basis (9%), performers (9%), adaptive pragmatics (10%), hedonists (11%) and digital individualists (6%).¹⁰

The milieus of immigrants have also been surveyed. The social welfare organization Caritas has

commissioned a study on migrant milieus in Germany¹¹, also conducted by Sinus Sociovision. On comparing migrant milieus with the milieus established for the general German population it shows that both do not differ fundamentally. Among migrants in Germany the traditional workers’ milieu (16%), the adaptive bourgeois milieu (16%) and the hedonist subcultural milieu (15%) are particularly widespread. Migrants whose deep religiosity influences their lifestyle significantly, on the other hand, only account for 7%.¹²

I do not propose to adopt the concept of social milieus the same way as established by Sinus-Sociovisions. My intention is rather to encourage a re-consideration of our conception of “migrants” and “culture”¹³. This can be done by not only considering the values, orientations and assumptions that individuals derive from their membership in diverse social groups (“cultural” factors) but also the social

status, income and education ("social condition"). This kind of conceptualization allows for a more detailed consideration of human behaviour, taking into account a variety of lifestyles and incomes. Talking about "the" Austrian, Serbian or Turkish "culture" by contrasting misleads to viewing the people as homogenous and unchangeable groups. Blaming "culture" for misunderstandings between patients and doctors does not explain anything and can even impede better communication (KNIPPER & BILGIN 2009: 7). Considering the different milieus on the other hand allows for a comparison between the problems of foreigners and locals who might share similar backgrounds. It furthermore renders visible that certain problems only affect a percentage of the migrant population, whereas the larger percentage does not show any medical or psychological particularities at all.

Migration and preventive health care as outlined by the Austrian Fund for Integration

Keeping in mind about what I have said above I shall discuss a literature survey that has been published by the Austrian Fund for Integration¹⁴ (MAYER 2011), and which is publicly accessible on their homepage¹⁵. Migrants are said to be a difficult-to-reach group for preventive measures in medicine, which according to the title of the study leads to a "dilemma". The paper describes the problem as follows: Even though migrants have a heightened need for preventive health care they cannot make use of the existing offers because these are designed for the middle class. They not only lack health literacy but also have little interest in preventive measures because they do not expect to be able to control their health status. The primary problem I can see in such argumentation is that almost everything that is attributed to a group called "migrants" could apply to low-income groups with little education in general. However, and as the paper itself repeatedly admits, migrants are a heterogeneous group, as not all of them earn low incomes. In fact, the second largest group of immigrants in Austria are Germans, who have a comparable level of income to Austrians.

Migrants are said to be psychologically vulnerable because of a lack of societal integration and participation. But similarly as "culture", also "integration" is a hard to define term. Is it enough to

share the language of the host country or does integration require the practice of "typical" Austrian or German traditions? If the latter is the case, then a lack of societal integration also applies to a whole range of social milieus from within the national boundaries, especially when thinking about the hedonist subculture. Moreover there is a huge gap between old and young people, both groups usually not sharing the same values. In the same vein a lack of societal participation not only affects migrants, but also marginalized groups like long-term unemployed, (some) single parents, physically and mentally handicapped, mentally ill, addicts, and a segment of the elderly.

A central problem the paper published by the Austrian Fund for Integration points out is that of language. This problem, however, does not relate to all types of migrants, but rather to immigrants from the first generation, among them in particular older women (KUTALEK 2011: 199). I fully understand that efficient communication is crucial for the clinical routine and that it is important to undertake measures to enhance the communication between doctors and patients. But even though language is a feature of culture I suggest that problem is specifically connected to language rather than culture-related, since this definition captures the problem more accurately.

The author cites "different concepts of illness" and "religious reasons that are assumed to cause illness" as cultural factors that "influence health because they shape ones individual lifestyle" (MAYER 2011: 10). Both would pose a "serious problem" (*ibid.* 18). I would like to point out that the German migrant milieu study accounts only 7% of immigrants to be deeply religious, which assumingly corresponds to the situation in Austria. Moreover many Austrians and Germans are also far from sharing purely biomedical beliefs, which can be seen in a booming esoteric sector offering fortune telling, natural healing, shamanism, faith healing and the like.

Another argument cited in the paper is that migrants often face psychic strain due to violence or torture before or during their migration. This, however, applies first and foremost to asylum seekers (political refugees), who are a much more homogenous group than "migrants" and thus should be named as such. It is important to note that their

problems result from political persecution and not from cultural otherness.

Also migration itself is posed as a stress factor, more precisely the process of acculturation and discrimination in the host country (HOFSTEDE 2001, cited from MAYER 2011; see also MACHLEIDT 2007a, b). I agree that the psychological effects of migration are an important scientific topic that should be explored and regarded. But we need to rethink how we implement such results into the non-scientific discourse. Most certainly we should not depict migrants as a group that is especially in need of help, socially weak, and in frail health, because this may result in a negative public opinion, which in itself poses a psychological risk to them (RAZUM & GEIGER 2003: 689, cited from MAYER 2011).

Conclusion

“Culture” in everyday language is mostly applied in accordance with national boundaries, language or religion instead of being contemplated in its anthropological meaning as a dynamic set of values, orientations, and habits that individuals derive from membership in diverse social groups. This easily leads to the misunderstanding that “cultural otherness” per se is a source of problems. A closer look, however, shows that the most often cited difficulties migrants face in health care such as a lack of language skills, emotional stress after persecution, or an unhealthy lifestyle rely on different factors, not all of them being “cultural”. Whereas the first cited problem might indeed be considered as “cultural” (in that language is considered as a primary feature of culture), the second rather is caused by political power structures and persecution than by culture and migration itself. The third problem not only affects migrants but the low-income earning population in general, which hardly makes it a direct consequence of migration.

In order to avoid culturalization I propose to specify more exactly about whom we are talking, e. g. by referring to the specific social milieus that are affected like “elderly male or female migrants from the first generation with little education” or “traumatized refugees”. This approach not only enables us to point out that the larger percentage of newcomers manages perfectly well with our health care system without being in need of special atten-

tion but also allows for comparisons with vulnerable groups in the general population, thus relativizing a common statement implicit to reporting in the media: “healthy local – sick migrant”.

Notes

1. Furthermore: symbolic forms or habit, depending on the underlying theoretical concept.
2. <http://derstandard.at/1256745563177/Ethnomedizin-Andere-Laender-andere-Schmerzen>
3. <http://derstandard.at/3341399/Schmerzenschreie-und-das-durchgestrichene-Schwein>
4. Truxal is a mild antipsychotic drug with strong sedative activity. The substance is known as Chlorprothixene; further trade-names are Cloxan and Taractan.
5. http://diepresse.com/home/panorama/integration/744149/Experten_Notstand-bei-Gesundheit-von-Migranten
6. “Viennese Blood” (“Wiener Blut”) is a famous operetta, written by the Austrian composer Johann Strauss.
7. Short for multicultural society.
8. <http://derstandard.at/3341399/Schmerzenschreie-und-das-durchgestrichene-Schwein>
9. Coverstory „Kranke Migranten“, in: Doktor in Wien, August 7th 2012, Verlag: Medizin Medien Austria GmbH.
10. For more information c. f.: www.integral.co.at/de/sinus/Folder_Sinus_Oesterreich_2011.pdf
11. <http://www.caritas.de/fuerprofis/fachthemen/migration/sinusmigranten>
12. There is no data on migrant milieus referring to Austria. The study however says that there are only fine distinctions between migrant groups in different countries.
13. For more detailed information on both categories compare Knipper/Bilgin 2009:16f
14. Österreichischer Integrationsfonds
15. http://www.integrationsfonds.at/oefif_dossiers/gesundheit/

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Manuscript received: March 01, 2013

Manuscript accepted: April 08, 2013

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